

PROMOTING SDG4 (QUALITY EDUCATION): THE INFLUENCE OF FAMILY ON CAREER DECISIONS AMONG ABM STUDENTS AT TACURONG NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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Promoting SDG4 (Quality Education): The Influence of Family on Career Decisions among ABM Students at Tacurong National High School

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Abstract

The study examines how family dynamics impact the career choices of students in the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) track, highlighting the role of familial support and guidance in achieving quality education and informed career decisions. It examined the relationship between family influence and career decisions within the context of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number four, focusing on Quality Education, among 161 ABM students at Tacurong National High School. It utilized a non-experimental quantitative research design employing descriptive-correlational techniques. Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression analysis were employed for data interpretation. Results revealed high levels of family influence and career decisions. Specifically, indicators such as parental engagement and cultural values received high ratings for family influence, while parental support obtained a very high rating and career actions received a high-rating for-career decision. A moderate positive correlation was observed between family influence and career decisions among ABM students. Furthermore, both domains of family influence, parental engagement, and cultural values, significantly influenced the career decisions of ABM students. Consequently, it is suggested that prioritizing initiatives aimed at enhancing parental engagement and fostering cultural values within the educational setting can effectively bolster the career decisions of ABM students at Tacurong National High School, aligning with the objectives of SDG4.

Keywords: *student, family influence, career decision, multiple regression analysis*

Introduction

Transitioning into early adulthood as a student can be quite challenging, this is because students must make important decisions about their careers, knowing that their choices will play a role in shaping the future of society (Wang & Jiao, 2022). Navigating this decision-making process is not straightforward, especially in today's rapidly changing world where careers can be unpredictable due to increased job mobility and the rise of gig economy opportunities. Planning a career involves a complex process of recognizing one's strengths, exploring education and job options, and aligning one's interests and skills. For some, finding the ideal career can be a lifelong journey, so it's important to have a clear career goal in mind before starting this expedition (Palabrica & Ferolino, 2023).

Choosing the right school subjects is crucial for students aiming for successful careers that shape their lives and contribute to society (Batool & Raiz, 2020; Van Dinh et al., 2019; Pratiwi et al., 2020; McKenzie et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Babajide & Esther, 2020; Orewere & Ojochogu, 2020). This decision is especially important for high school students (Sahu et al., 2021; Quisyi et al., 2020). The family plays a key role in this process, acting as a vital support unit, offering information, guidance, and often serving as role models, especially parents (Jemini-Gashi & Kadriu, 2022).

In Filipino culture, respecting elders and relying on parents for financial support strongly shape students' career decisions. Children, dependent on their parents, tend to follow their decisions, overshadowing the influence of peers and relatives. Tuition affordability and scholarships also play a big role in how family significantly influences the career decisions of Filipino students (Ouano et al., 2019). Therefore, it's crucial to acknowledge that families, especially parents and guardians, significantly influence their children's career aspirations (Quiño, 2022). Moreover, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development emphasizes the importance of family-focused policies in achieving SDG targets related to education, health, and well-being, recognizing the substantial influence of families on individuals' career paths (Butt, 2019). A survey conducted by Batool and Raiz in 2020 with 300 students highlighted how parental decisions strongly affect students' career decisions. Additionally, research has shown that some students choose careers to meet their parents' expectations or because of family and cultural values, which can sometimes limit their future career opportunities (Griffin & Hu, 2019).

Despite prior research by Batool and Raiz (2020) and Quio (2022), there remains a critical need for further investigation into how families influence children's career decisions, particularly within the context of Tacurong City. Existing studies lack specific insights relevant to Tacurong National High School. Fahmi and Ali (2022) have identified various factors affecting career planning but underscore the necessity for additional research. This study seeks to address this significant gap in knowledge.

Research Objectives

The primary aim of this quantitative research study is to examine the influence of family on the career decisions made by students enrolled in ABM programs at Tacurong NHS. More specifically, the research has the following quantitative objectives:

1. To determine the level of family influence in two dimensions:
 - 1.1. parental engagement; and

- 1.2. culture of values.
2. To evaluate the level of career decisions in terms of:
 - 1.1. parental support; and
 - 1.2. career action.
3. To determine the relationship between family influence and career decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management students.
4. To determine which domain of family influences the career decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design with a descriptive-correlational approach. Descriptive research design involves observing and describing a subject's behavior without influencing it (Shuttleworth, 2019). Its main goal is to describe various aspects of individuals, situations, or phenomena in their natural state (Siedlecki, 2020). Correlational research design, on the other hand, examines relationships between variables without researcher manipulation (Bhandari, 2023). This type of study assesses the strength and direction of correlations, which can be either positive or negative (Cherry, 2023). These methods allowed the researchers to observe and describe family dynamics' specific impact on the career decisions of ABM students. Without exerting influence, the correlational method specifically explored relationships between variables like family influence and career decisions, facilitating a quantitative analysis. This approach enhances insights into the interplay between family's influence and career decisions of ABM students.

Participants

The study employed purposive sampling, a scientific method of non-probability sampling, to select participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the study's goals (Crossman, 2019). Participants consisted solely of students enrolled in ABM strand at Tacurong National High School for the 2023 – 2024 academic year. With a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, the Raosoft tool was used to calculate the sample size of 161 students. This selection method ensured that the chosen participants were representative of the ABM student population at the school. Participants outside the study's location were excluded, and respondents were given the freedom to withdraw if they felt uncomfortable or perceived any risks to their well-being during the research process.

Data collection occurred in February 2024, ensuring the timeliness and relevance of the gathered information.

Instruments

The survey on family influence is adapted from Alves and Gama (2020). The said instrument is designed to measure the influence of families on students' career decisions based on two factors, namely: parental engagement and culture of values. The responses of the study respondents were interpreted using the scale below:

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that family influence is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that family influence is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that family influence is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that family influence is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that family influence is not observed.

The survey instrument for career decisions is adapted from the study of Xing and Rojewski (2018). The instrument is designed to measure the career decisions of the students based on two factors, namely: parental support and career actions. Responses of the study respondents was interpreted using the scale:

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that career decisions are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that career decisions are oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that career decisions are sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that career decisions are rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that career decisions are not observed.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the research was sought from the school authorities. Subsequently, the questionnaire underwent validation by experienced validators, resulting in an excellent rating of 5. A pilot test involving students at Tacurong National High School was conducted to assess the questionnaire's reliability, where Cronbach's alpha was utilized. Cronbach's alpha, a widely used measure of internal consistency, has expanded in its reliability applications over time (Amirrudin et al., 2021). When interpreting Cronbach's alpha, the generally accepted guideline is as follows: $\alpha \geq 0.9$ is considered excellent, $0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$ is good, $0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$ is acceptable, $0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$ is questionable, $0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$ is poor, and $0.5 > \alpha$ is considered unacceptable (George & Mallery, 2003).

The dependent variable garnered a rating of 0.83, interpreted as good, while the independent variable also received a rating of 0.80, also interpreted as good. Upon establishing the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the researchers then initiated a full-blast survey. Subsequently, the researchers carefully analyzed and interpreted the data, ensuring all acquired data and information were treated with utmost confidentiality, exclusively for research purposes.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools was used to tail and handle the data collected from the questionnaires: Mean. This was used to determine the level of family influence and career decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management Students. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was applied to establish the significance of the relationship between family influence and career decisions. Multiple Regression. This was employed to identify the significant predictors of Career Decisions.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study, the researcher maintained ethical principles and standards by diligently adhering to the study protocol, assessments, and standardized criteria. Notably, these guidelines were strictly followed regarding population management and data handling, as outlined below:

Voluntary Participation: Respondents in this study were given the choice to participate or not, at their discretion. Potential respondents were approached and provided with an explanation procedure, including detailed information on their rights to withdraw or refuse the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality: Respondents were not compelled to disclose personal information if they chose not to. Researchers respected respondents' privacy and ensured no harm or coercion was inflicted upon them.

Informed Consent Process: Respondents were adequately informed about the study's purpose, risks, benefits, and their rights. Sufficient time was provided for them to read and understand the materials, ask questions, and voice concerns.

Plagiarism: Proper recognition and citation of all sources were ensured to avoid plagiarism or irregularity. Additionally, Turnitin plagiarism detector was utilized.

Fabrication: The study was based on reliable investigations, ensuring that the researcher did not fabricate data or conclusions but accurately represented existing literature.

Falsification: Data were not embellished or misrepresented to fit preconceived notions or false claims.

Conflict of Interest (COI): Data collection techniques that could result in a conflict of interest were avoided. The study focused solely on the validity of analytical results and the well-being of respondents, without being influenced by any side interests.

Deceit: Respondents were assured that providing information would not harm them, and the researcher did not deceive or dishonestly manipulate them.

Permission from Organization/Location: Written authorization was obtained from proper authorities.

Authorship: Contributions of individuals were accurately represented, with the research adviser considered a co-author. Co-authors must secure consent from others before using the study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Family Influence on Accountancy, Business, and Management Students

Table 1 illustrates the level of family influence on students studying ABM at Tacurong NHS. The total mean score for family influence was 4.07, indicating a high level. This implies that students in Accountancy, Business, and Management oftentimes observe family influence. The two indicators are disclosed as follows: Parental Engagement achieved a mean rating of 4.08, and Cultural Values received a mean rating of 4.05, indicating that both are oftentimes observed.

Table 1. *Level of Family Influence*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
<i>Parental Engagement</i>	4.08	High
<i>Cultural Values</i>	4.05	High
<i>Overall</i>	4.07	High

Level of Career Decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management Students

Table 2 below presents the level of career decisions among ABM students of Tacurong NHS. The total mean score is 4.08, indicating a high level. The two indicators are disclosed as follows: Parental Support achieved a mean rating of 4.28, indicating it is always

achieved. On the other hand, Career Action received a mean rating of 3.95, suggesting that it is only observed oftentimes.

Table 2. *Level of Career Decisions*

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Parental Support	4.22	Very High
Career Action	3.95	High
Overall	4.08	High

Significant Relationship between Family Influence and Career Decisions

Table 3 presents the computed r-value of 0.650, which fell to the moderate positive correlation, and the computed p-value at 0.000. This indicates a significant direct relationship between family influence and career decisions among ABM students of Tacurong NHS. Furthermore, the null hypothesis of this study was rejected since the p-value was lower than the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3. *Significant relationship between Family Influence on Career Decisions of ABM students in Tacurong NHS*

Category	p-value	r-value	Significant
Family Influence vs Career Decisions	P<0.000	0.650**	Moderate Positive Correlation

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Family Influence Domains towards Career Decisions of ABM Students

The interpretation of Table 4 indicates that in the computed multiple regression analysis examining how family influence domains impact career decisions, both parental engagement and cultural values exhibited significant effects on career decisions, with p-values of .001 and .000, respectively. Given that the estimated p-values for parental engagement and cultural values are below the significance threshold of 0.05, null hypothesis number 2, which posits that family does not significantly influence the career decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management students, is rejected. Consequently, it can be concluded that these markers have a considerable impact on career decisions.

Table 4. *Multiple Regression Analysis of the Family Influence Domains towards Career Decisions*

	Career Decisions	
Family Influence	p-value	
Parental Engagement	.001	Significant
Cultural Values	.000	Significant

Level of Family Influence on Accountancy, Business, and Management Students

The findings presented in Table 1 closely align with the assertions made by Amarnani et al. (2018) regarding the significance of parental engagement in indicating individuals' value to important others, indirectly contributing to career development and persistence. Twani et al. (2020) also highlight the influence of culture, family, and friends on shaping career decisions, which resonates with our results. Furthermore, Esterhuysen et al. (2019) mention various factors influencing students' perceptions of jobs, including advice from school, parental and teacher influence, and cultural upbringing.

Level of Career Decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management Students

The results shown in Table 2 resonate with Alextian and Abdullah's (2020) assertion that parental support plays a vital role among young individuals when it comes to making career decisions. They suggest that such support correlates positively with career decision-making. Similarly, the findings align with the conclusions drawn by Hariko and Aggriana (2019), emphasizing the importance of career actions. They highlight the significance of understanding oneself, career goals, and realistic reasoning to facilitate effective career decision-making. Therefore, our results affirm the crucial roles of both parental support and individual career actions in guiding students toward informed career pathways.

Significant Relationship between Family Influence and Career Decisions

Contrary to the findings gathered by Giang and Nhung (2022) in their study, which suggested that family factors have no relationship with career choices, our results debunk this notion. According to our findings in Table 3, there is a significant influence of family on career decisions, thus contradicting the conclusions drawn in their study. In addition to our findings, Kocak et al. (2021) discovered that individuals' career decision-making self-efficacy is primarily shaped by their families and academic satisfaction. They noted that families play a significant role in shaping their children's interests and values, fostering self-concepts, and providing both positive and negative perspectives on professions.

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Family Influence Domains towards Career Decisions of Accountancy, Business, and Management Students

The findings in Table 4 align with previous research, as observed by Sanni et al. (2024), who noted that parents generally maintain positive perceptions of their children's career choices. Similarly, Ekeng et al. (2022) emphasized the significant impact of parental engagement on their children's career success, a notion echoed by Li et al. (2020), highlighting the pivotal role of parental engagement in career-related matters for promoting successful career adaptation. Moreover, the influence of culture emerges as a crucial determinant in students' major decisions, as emphasized by Vu (2020). Additionally, Bakke (2021) highlighted the significance of cultural notions, such as work-centrality, in shaping teenagers' reflections about career choices.

Conclusions

The findings show that the level of family influence is high, which means that this is oftentimes observed by the ABM students at Tacurong National High School. Meanwhile, both indicators, parental engagement and cultural values, received a high rating, implying that these indicators are often observed by the ABM students at Tacurong National High School.

The results show that the level of career decisions is high, indicating that this is oftentimes observed by the ABM students at Tacurong National High School. On the other hand, parental support obtained a very high rating, while career action obtained a high rating, meaning these indicators are always and often observed, respectively.

Family influence has a moderate positive relationship with the career decisions ABM students at Tacurong National High School.

Both domains of family influence, parental engagement, and cultural values, have demonstrated significant effects on the career decisions of ABM students at Tacurong National High School.

Given the high level of family influence observed among ABM students at Tacurong National High School, it is recommended to enhance family involvement in students' career development journeys. The researcher recommends that for this to be achieved, students and their parents may be engaged through workshops, seminars, and communication channels aimed at fostering parental engagement and reinforcing cultural values that support career decisions.

Given that students make a lot of decisions about their careers, the researchers advise offering thorough career advising programs and tools. These courses ought to help students define their professional objectives and create practical strategies to meet them.

Given the moderate positive relationship between family influence and career decisions, the researchers recommend that efforts should be made to foster positive family dynamics that support students' career development. This involves promoting open communication, mutual respect, and understanding within families to create a conducive environment for career exploration and decision-making.

Based on the significant impact shown by both parental engagement and cultural values on the career decisions of ABM students at Tacurong National High School, it is recommended to encourage more involvement of parents and to promote cultural awareness among students. This can be done through activities and programs aimed at fostering communication between parents and students, as well as activities that highlight the importance of cultural diversity in career choices.

Future researchers should explore more variables and indicators that may have a relationship to family influence and career decisions.

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